

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activities of some Thiosemicarbazides and Mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles

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Thiosemicarbazides (1a-j) were synthesised by the condensation of some hydrazides with substituted-phenyl isothiocyanates. These thiosemicarbazides were cyclised to provide various mercaptotriazoles (2a-j). The antibacterial and antifungal activities of the compounds were tested against some species of bacteria and fungi.

Thiosemicarbazides exhibit potential and diverse biological activities¹. Mercaptotriazoles which are obtained by the cyclisation of thiosemicarbazides, have been reported as antimicrobial agents². In view of the immense biological importance of these compounds it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some new compounds in this series and to test their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

1a-e, 2a-e; R=2-F-C₆H₄NH
1f-j, 2f-j; R=4-F-C₆H₄NH
1a f, 2a f; R₁=4-ClC₆H₄
1b, g, 2b g; R₁=4-BrC₆H₄
1c, h, 2c h; R₁=2-MeC₆H₄
1d, i, 2d, i; R₁=4-MeC₆H₄
1e, j, 2e, j; R₁=3,4-(Me)₂C₆H₄

In the present investigation some substituted thiosemicarbazides (1a-j) were synthesised by the condensation of *N*-(2-fluoro)- and *N*-(4-fluoro)-phenylmalonic acid hydrazides with some substituted phenyl isothiocyanates. These substituted thiosemicarbazides were then cyclised to give the mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (2a-j).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1a-j AND 2a-j*

Compd. no.	M p. °C	Yield %	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹
1a	139	71	3 180 (NH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 070 (C=S), 1 250 (C-F), 750 (C-Cl)
b	165	74	3 180 (NH), 1 630 (C=O), 1 070 (C=S), 1 250 (C=F), 600 (C-Br)
c	147	70	3 180 (NH), 1 655 (C=O), 1 100 (C=S), 1 250 (C-F)
d	120	76	3 180 (NH), 1 660 (C=O), 1 120 (C=S), 1 250 (C-F)
e	196	67	3 180 (NH), 1 655 (C=O), 1 100 (C=S), 1 250 (C-F)
f	135	60	3 180 (NH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 070 (C=S), 1 250 (C-F), 750 (C-Cl)
g	155	52	3 180 (NH), 1 630 (C=O), 1 100 (C=S), 1 260 (C-F), 600 (C-Br)
h	101	70	3 180 (NH), 1 640 (C=O), 1 110 (C=S), 1 280 (C-F)
i	167	64	3 180 (NH), 1 660 (C=O), 1 100 (C=S), 1 300 (C-F)
j	117	73	3 180 (NH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 070 (C=S), 1 250 (C-F)
2a	213	69	3 200 (NH), 2 550 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 100 (C-F), 750 (C-Cl)
b	247	74	3 200 (NH), 2 600 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 200 (C-F), 600 (C-Br)
c	189	70	3 200 (NH), 2 550 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 200 (C-F)
d	166	73	3 200 (NH), 2 550 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 250 (C-F)
e	201	84	3 200 (NH), 2 550 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 250 (C-F)
f	228	71	3 200 (NH), 2 550 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 250 (C-F)
g	219	79	3 200 (NH), 2 550 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 260 (C-F)
h	192	67	3 200 (NH), 2 600 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 250 (C-F)
i	174	64	3 200 (NH), 2 550 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 300 (C-F)
j	237	79	3 200 (NH), 2 600 (SH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 250 (C-F)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of Merck made. Melting points were taken using a Thomas-Hoover apparatus in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer.

N-(4-Chloro)phenylthiosemicarbazide of *N*-(2-fluoro)phenylmalonamic acid hydrazide (**1a**): A solution of *N*-(2-fluoro)phenylmalonamic acid hydrazide (0.2 g, 0.001 mol) and 4-chlorophenyl isothiocyanate (0.17 g, 0.001 mol) separately dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting white crystalline solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (72%), m.p. 139° (Found: C, 51.27; H, 3.75; N, 15.02. C₁₆H₁₄N₄O₂ClS calcd. for: C, 50.39; H, 3.67; N, 14.69%). Similarly (**1b**–**c**) were prepared by taking suitably substituted phenyl isothiocyanates and another series (**1f**–**j**) prepared by condensing *N*-(4-fluoro)phenylmalonamic acid hydrazide with the same phenyl isothiocyanates.

3-Mercapto-4-(4-chloro)phenyl-5-[*N'*-(2'-fluoro)phenyl]acetamido-1,2,4-triazole (**2a**): A suspension of *N*-(4-chloro)phenylthiosemicarbazide (**1a**) of *N*-(2-fluoro)phenylmalonamic acid hydrazide (0.38 g, 0.001 mol) in an aqueous solution of NaOH (4%; 5 ml) was gently refluxed for 4 h till a clear solution was obtained. After cooling, the solution was filtered from suspended impurities. The filtrate was adjusted to pH 5–6 with dilute HCl at 5–10°. The separated dirty white solid was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (69.05%), m.p. 213° (Found: C, 53.70; H, 3.51; S, 8.02, C₁₆H₁₂N₄O FClS calcd. for: C, 52.89; H, 3.30; S, 81.81%).

Similarly other derivatives (**2b**–**j**) were prepared by cyclising compounds **1b**–**j** (Table 1).

The filter paper disc method³ was used for screening the compounds (**1a**–**j**, **2a**–**j**) for their in vitro antimicrobial activity; antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium citrinum* and *Fusarium moniliforme*, using Czapek's Dox Agar medium and antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* using nutrient agar medium. It was observed that the halogen substituted compounds (**1a**, **b**, **f**, **g**, **2a**, **b**, **f**, **g**) exhibited activities and rest of the compounds were not significantly active at 250 and 500 ppm concentrations.

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